

Spectral model of the nonlinear dynamics of neuroblastoma

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ABSTRACT

A novel spectral model of neuroblastoma dynamics is proposed. This model is based on an extended nonlinear "tumor–immunity" system of equations, accounting for tumor heterogeneity, the immune response, and the pharmacokinetics of therapy. To address the stiff system, a hybrid Padé [2/2]-Adomian-MsDTM approach is employed, which reformulates the problem as recurrent algebraic relations. The model parameters are linked to morphological and immunological characteristics (Shimada classification), enabling patient-specific adaptation without increasing system dimensionality. The Padé approximation is shown numerically to expand the convergence domain and suppress boundary oscillations under sharp therapeutic interventions. The model provides a computationally efficient framework for simulating disease dynamics and evaluating individualized chemotherapy regimens; clinical validation on patient cohorts is an identified next step.

Keywords: neuroblastoma, mathematical modeling, spectral methods, differential transformation method, Adomian polynomials, Padé approximation, MsDTM, oncodynamics, personalized therapy.

1. Introduction

Neuroblastoma remains one of the most aggressive and prognostically unpredictable solid tumors of childhood [1,2]. The high mortality in high-risk patients is due not only to the primary tumor mass but also to the complex nonlinear interplay among heterogeneous cell populations, the stromal component, and the systemic immune response [3,4]. The phenotypic plasticity of neuroblasts, the ability of these cells to transition from a differentiated adrenergic state to a more resistant mesenchymal state under the influence of therapy and microenvironmental factors, plays a significant role in disease progression [5,6].

A mathematical description of these processes requires systems of nonlinear differential equations that account for competition among tumor clones, immune responses, and therapeutic effects [3,7]. However, such models exhibit pronounced stiffness: rapid changes in dynamics at the time of drug administration substantially undermine the stability of standard numerical methods, including Runge–Kutta schemes, thereby limiting their applicability in real-time clinical decision support [1,6,8,9].

The shift toward personalized medicine demands not only qualitative insight but also computationally stable prediction of disease dynamics in near-real time. Particular difficulty arises in modeling bolus and infusion chemotherapy regimens, which cause abrupt changes in phase variables. An additional requirement is the integration of morphological and clinical markers (e.g., Shimada criteria) directly into the structure of dynamic models [4,10].

The classical foundations of mathematical oncology were laid in the works of Kuznetsov et al. and Adam & Bellomo, where tumor-immune system interactions are described by nonlinear differential systems [3,11]. These approaches were further extended in a clinical context by De Bernardi et al. [12]. Subsequently, spectral methods enabling a transition from the differential form of models to recurrent algebraic equations have been actively used to improve computational efficiency. The Adomian decomposition method (ADM) enables analytical approximations of nonlinear models without linearization [7,8], whereas the differential transform method (DTM) is widely applied in biomedical problems because of its high computational efficiency [9,14,15]. Moreover, the classical DTM, which is based on power series, has a limited radius of convergence. The use of Padé approximations partially removes this limitation but may introduce spurious poles within the integration interval [16-18].

Despite these advances, neuroblastoma modeling requires simultaneous consideration of the multistage nature of therapy and instantaneous changes in system dynamics. The concept of the multistage differential transform method (MsDTM) [8,19] enables local solution reconstruction; however, its integration with Adomian polynomials and rational Padé regularization for oncodynamics problems remains largely unexplored. The implementation of such integration requires structured data obtained from automated tumor morphology analysis [20,21]. In this work, a database of histological indicators designed via an object-oriented approach is employed [22].

The present study proposes an extended spectral architecture that combines a multistage DTM, Adomian polynomials, and fixed-order Padé approximations. Unlike existing approaches, the proposed scheme provides a computationally robust semi-analytical description of system dynamics under discontinuous therapeutic interventions while preserving computational efficiency in multistage integration. This creates a foundation for building decision-support systems in personalized oncology.

The main purpose of this work is to develop a spectral model of neuroblastoma dynamics based on the MsDTM integrated with Adomian polynomials and rational Padé regularization, providing robust numerical behavior and computational efficiency in the analysis of therapeutic regimens.

2. Mathematical Model of Neuroblastoma Dynamics

Let $x = x_A + x_M$ denote the total tumor cell density. As the initial mathematical model of neuroblastoma dynamics, we adopt an extended system of ordinary differential equations of the «tumor-immunity» type, rooted in the framework of Kuznetsov et al. [3] and extended by de Pillis et al. [1]. The system describes the dynamics of five interacting components: adrenergic tumor cells (x_A), mesenchymal tumor cells (x_M), immune effector cells (z), the neuropil (p), and the drug concentration (c):

$$\dot{x}_A = \alpha_A x_A \left(1 - \frac{x}{K}\right) - \beta_A x_A z - \gamma_A c x_A + \varphi_M x_M - \varphi_A x_A, \quad (1)$$

$$\dot{x}_M = \alpha_M x_M \left(1 - \frac{x}{K}\right) - \beta_M x_M z - \gamma_M c x_M + \varphi_A x_A - \varphi_M x_M, \quad (2)$$

$$\dot{p} = \sigma - \mu p - \delta_p x p + \rho_p p z, \quad (3)$$

$$\dot{z} = \lambda x z - \nu z + \xi x, \quad (4)$$

$$\dot{c} = -k_e c + u(t), \quad (5)$$

where $u(t)$ is the therapeutic intervention (chemotherapy intensity).

The parameters φ_A and φ_M define the rates of phenotypic transition from the adrenergic to the mesenchymal state and vice versa. To account for the asymmetric nature of this plasticity under therapeutic pressure, they are expressed as:

$$\varphi_A = c_A \cdot \varphi(S), \quad \varphi_M = c_M \cdot \varphi(S),$$

where c_A and c_M are fixed scaling constants, and $\varphi(S)$ is the integral stress-dependent plasticity function.

To avoid discontinuity in the right-hand side - which would violate the analyticity requirement of the differential transformation method — the transition from nominal to stress-modulated immune stimulation is regularized via a smooth sigmoid function. Specifically, the effective immune stimulation rate in Eq. (4) is defined as:

$$\lambda_{eff}(S) = \lambda + (\lambda_{max} - \lambda) \cdot \frac{S^n}{S_{50}^n + S^n},$$

where $S \in [0,1]$ is the systemic stress index, $S_{50} = 0.5$, $n = 8$ (sharp but C^∞ transition), and $\lambda_{max} = \lambda_{eff0}(1 + l_1)$.

Thus Eq. (4) becomes:

$$\dot{z} = \lambda_{eff}(S) \cdot x z - \nu z + \xi x.$$

This preserves the biological interpretation (immune exhaustion at high stress) while ensuring infinite differentiability, which is essential for the Taylor series expansion underpinning the MsDTM-Padé scheme.

The term $\lambda x z$ in (4) represents immune stimulation proportional to total tumor burden (combined antigenic signal from both subpopulations). The term $+\rho_p z$ reflects the positive influence of immune effector cells on the stromal component (neuropil). In favorable (low-risk) forms of neuroblastoma according to the Shimada classification, lymphocytic infiltration promotes tumor differentiation and neuropil maturation, which is associated with a more favorable prognosis [4,12]. In high-risk cases, this effect is weakened, but it is retained in the model as a general microenvironmental mechanism.

For system dynamics analysis and control synthesis, weighted parameters characterizing the current biological status of the heterogeneous tumor are introduced [12,25]:

$$\alpha = \frac{\alpha_A x_A + \alpha_M x_M}{x}, \quad \beta = \frac{\beta_A x_A + \beta_M x_M}{x}, \quad \gamma = \frac{\gamma_A x_A + \gamma_M x_M}{x}.$$

These parameters reflect the integral proliferative activity, immunogenicity, and therapeutic sensitivity of the tumor, respectively:

- **Proliferative activity (α):** reflects the total growth rate, which is dependent on morphological Shimada features (nuclear-cytoplasmic ratio, nuclear atypia) [4,5].
- **Immunogenicity (β):** characterizes the efficiency of immune cytotoxicity, which is modulated by tumor lymphocytic infiltration (TILs) [3,26].
- **Cytotoxic sensitivity (γ):** a key control parameter. During treatment, selective elimination of the sensitive fraction x_A leads to a decrease in the integral value of γ , which mathematically describes the mechanism of resistance development and the risk of relapse [12,27].

Model parameterization (Table 1) is performed via analytical dependencies on morphometric and immunological indicators (Shimada classification). The calculation of these indicators (nuclear-cytoplasmic ratio R_{NC} , MKI, and atypia) is implemented on the basis of a patented method [21] and an algorithm for automated analysis of digital images [23]. This allows adaptation of system dynamics to the specific risk group of the patient [4,10,12,13,24].

Table 1

Model parameterization on the basis of morphofunctional characteristics

Coefficient	Parametric formula	Biological meaning
α – growth rate	$\alpha = \alpha_0(1 + \alpha_1 R_{NC} + \alpha_2 A_{\text{atypia}})$, where $R_{NC} = S_n/S_c$, S_n – mean nuclear area; S_c – mean cytoplasmic area	Acceleration of proliferation at high nuclear–cytoplasmic ratio (R_{NC}) and nuclear atypia (A_{atypia}).
K – carrying capacity	$K = K_0(1 + b_1 n + b_2 m)$, where n – normalized cell density, m – nuclear atypia index	Limitation of maximum tumor volume by cell density and neuropil maturity.
β – immune cytolysis	$\beta = \beta_0(1 + c_1 \eta_{TIL})$	Tumor growth suppression by lymphocytic infiltration.
μ – neuropil degradation	$\mu = \mu_0(1 + d_1 MKI)$	Natural neuropil degradation accelerated by high mitotic activity (MKI).
σ – immune activation	$\sigma = \sigma_0(1 + s_1 MKI)$	Immune response intensity at high MKI .
ρ – immune support of stroma	$\rho = \rho_0(1 + r_1 \eta_{TIL})$	Positive effect of immune cells on neuropil maturation.
λ_{eff} – tumor-induced immune activation	$\lambda_{eff} = \lambda_{eff_0}(1 + l_1 \cdot \sigma(S))$, where $\sigma(S) = S^n/(S_{50}^n + S^n)$ is a smooth sigmoid with $S_{50} = 0.5, n = 8$. This replaces λ in Eq. (4) and models the transition from immune activation to exhaustion under systemic stress S .	Enhancement of tumor-induced immune activation under systemic stress. At high values of S , the parameter λ_{eff} captures the compensatory immune hyperactivation that precedes immune exhaustion.
δ – tissue degradation	$\delta = \delta_0(1 + e_1 S)$	Neuropil destruction due to toxicity and stress.
γ – therapy effect	$\gamma = \gamma_0(1 + g_1 S)$	Cytotoxic drug effect modulated by organism state.
φ – phenotypic plasticity	$\varphi = \varphi_0(1 + f_1 S)$	Rate of transition between adrenergic (x_A) and mesenchymal (x_M) states under systemic stress (S).

The variable $S(t) \in [0,1]$ is normalized to the unit interval via the scaling parameter θ , which absorbs patient-specific toxicity thresholds. To mathematically close the model and ensure its reproducibility, we define $S(t)$ through an instantaneous algebraic mapping to the current drug concentration $c(t)$:

$$S(t) = \theta \cdot c(t),$$

where θ characterizes the patient's individual drug sensitivity and systemic toxicity threshold.

This formulation enables modeling of reduced immune efficiency and degradation of healthy tissues during aggressive treatment [12,13,27] without increasing the differential dimensionality of the system. We acknowledge that this linear instantaneous mapping $S(t) = \theta \cdot c(t)$ is a deliberate simplification: cumulative toxicity in practice exhibits pharmacodynamic lag and saturation effects.

This simplification is justified here by three considerations:

1. the sigmoid $\lambda_{eff}(S)$ with exponent $n = 8$ already introduces a strongly nonlinear mapping from drug concentration to immune dynamics;
2. the parameter θ can be calibrated per patient from pharmacokinetic data, absorbing inter-individual variability;
3. $S(t)$ can be replaced by a Hill-type E_{max} pharmacodynamic model in future extensions without structural changes to the spectral scheme. This limitation is explicitly addressed in Section 6.1, where cumulative toxicity and delayed pharmacodynamic effects are analyzed.

The proposed parameterization approach ensures functional correspondence with the Shimada classification [4,10], since each system parameter is a function of the morphological and immunological characteristics that determine the prognostic risk group. This approach addresses several key clinical challenges [4,10,12,13,27]:

- **Accounting for interpatient heterogeneity**, individual disease variability is captured without expanding the system dimensionality [3,13].
- **Personalization of dynamics**: adaptation of tumor growth, the immune response, and pharmacodynamic processes to a specific biological profile while preserving model compactness [4].
- **Individualization of therapy**: the optimal control algorithm $u_i^*(t)$ and calculation of the optimal exposure time T_i^* are derived from personalized model parameters, enabling the formation of individual treatment protocols [12].
- **Clinical interpretability**: Each formula in the model structure has a clear biological meaning and is based on verifiable neuroblastoma risk markers (age, stage, and molecular-genetic profile of a specific patient) [4,10].

To transform the initial mathematical model (1)-(5) into a stable spectral form, the following principles of parameter formation are used [9,14,28]:

1. **Base values**: Coefficients with the index “0” (α_0, K_0 , etc.) determine the initial rates of processes (tumor growth, immune recruitment) for a standard clinical case. In the transition to the spectral model, they serve as the basis for calculating all subsequent series coefficients, adapting the general equations to a specific risk group [28].

2. **Weight coefficients:** multipliers (α_1, b_1, \dots) determine the degree of influence of biological markers on system behavior. They convert static Shimada classification indicators (e.g., MKI) into dynamic weights that directly enter the spectral equations [29,30].
3. **Normalization:** To ensure computational stability, all morphometric features and the systemic factor index $S(t)$ are used in normalized form on the interval $[0,1]$. This allows the model to maintain accuracy for any numerical values of input data [27,30].

3. Spectral Modeling Based on the Hybrid Padé-Adomian-MsDTM Method

For numerical analysis of the extended dynamic system (1)-(5), a hybrid approach is applied that combines the capabilities of the MsDTM, spectral Adomian polynomials, and rational Padé regularization. This approach transforms the initial mathematical model into a system of recurrent algebraic relations, simplifying numerical analysis and providing high prediction accuracy in the presence of rapid phase transitions between tumor cell states.

3.1. Differential Transform Method

The spectral model is constructed via the differential transformation method of G. E. Pukhov [9,14]. The method transforms continuous state functions $x(t)$ into their spectral representation: a sequence of discrete functions $X(k)$ of integer arguments $k = 0, 1, 2, \dots$. The direct transformation for each variable of the system (tumor subpopulations x_A, x_M , neuropil p , immune response z , and drug concentration c) is computed via the following formula:

$$X(k) = \frac{H^k}{k!} \left[\frac{d^k x(t)}{dt^k} \right]_{t=t_0}, \quad (6)$$

where H - is a scaling coefficient with the dimension of argument t and is often taken equal to the length of the interval $0 \leq t \leq H$ on which the function $x(t)$ is considered. The sequence $X(k)$ is called the differential spectrum of the function $x(t)$.

The inverse transformation reconstructs the original $x(t)$ from the images $X(k)$ in the form of a Taylor power series:

$$x(t) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \left(\frac{t-t_0}{H} \right)^k X(k). \quad (7)$$

Here, and below $\tau = \frac{t-t_{i-1}}{T_i} \in [0,1]$ is the dimensionless local time in the i -th therapy stage, where $T_i = H$ is the stage duration (in MsDTM, the scaling coefficient H is taken equal to T_i).

The radius of convergence of the series $\rho = H \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \left| \frac{X(k)}{X(k+1)} \right|$ determines the method's limitation on large time intervals.

For correct approximation, the condition $H < \rho$ must be satisfied.

To model long-term neuroblastoma expansion, the MsDTM [8] is needed, in which the total observation interval is divided into a number of subintervals of equal length, and a local approximation is constructed on each subinterval propagating the boundary values as initial conditions for the next stage. This minimizes error accumulation but requires additional stabilization of the solution at step boundaries [19].

3.2. Processing Nonlinearities via Adomian Polynomial Convolutions

A key feature of neuroblastoma dynamics is the presence of cross nonlinearities of the types $x_A z$ and $x_M z$ (immune cytotoxicity). To represent them in spectral form without linearization, Adomian polynomials [7] are used. In spectral space, this approach is implemented by computing nonlinear terms as discrete convolutions. This preserves the full nonlinear behavior of the model when describing sharp changes in the cell population density under the influence of chemotherapy $u(t)$ [7,30].

In general, the nonlinear function $Q(x)$ is approximated by the series $\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} A_k$, where the components A_k are determined analytically through the parameter s [30]:

$$A_k = \frac{1}{k!} \left\{ \frac{d^k}{ds^k} \left[Q \left(\sum_{i=0}^k s^i X(i) \right) \right] \right\}_{s=0}, \quad (8)$$

However, for numerical implementation within the spectral model, we restrict ourselves to a finite number of spectrum discretized $k = 0, 1, \dots, N$.

For the most common nonlinearities in this model-products of two variables ($f \cdot g$) or squares (x^2) characteristic of systems (1)-(5) - the Adomian procedure within the i -th MsDTM stage reduces to computing finite discrete convolutions:

$$A_k(f \cdot g) = \sum_{m=0}^k F_q(m) G_q(k-m), \quad k = 0, 1, \dots, N, \quad (9)$$

where f and g denote arbitrary model variables (e.g., x_A and z , or x and p); $F_q(k)$ and $G_q(k)$ are their differential spectra.

This approach allows the values of nonlinear terms to be computed at each recursion step using only the already found coefficients of previous orders within the current subinterval. This ensures high solution accuracy without linearization

of the system; however, like the Taylor method, this construction is sensitive to the radius of convergence, requiring the introduction of rational regularization at each stage.

3.3. Rational Padé [2/2] Approximation

In oncodynamics problems characterized by high system stiffness due to significant differences in the rates of cell proliferation and drug degradation, the classical polynomial Taylor approximation can generate spurious oscillations at interval boundaries. To regularize the solution at each therapy stage, a rational Padé approximant of order $[m/n]$ is used - a rational function of the form [16,17]:

$$R_{m,n}(\tau) = \frac{P_m(\tau)}{Q_n(\tau)} \quad (10)$$

which coincides with the original Taylor series up to order $m + n$; τ is the dimensionless local time defined in Section 3.1.

The polynomials $P_m(\tau)$ and $Q_n(\tau)$ are determined from the spectrum coefficients $X(k)$ as follows:

1. **Numerator** $P_m(\tau)$: a modified segment of the Taylor series that preserves information about system dynamics at small intervals.
2. **Denominator** $Q_n(\tau)$: a correcting polynomial that suppresses the divergence of the series at the boundaries of interval H .

For stiff systems such as (1)-(5), where the drug concentration decays rapidly ($k_e = 0.45$) while tumor growth evolves on a much slower time scale, numerical stability requires an A-stable rational approximant. Among Padé schemes compatible with $N = 5$ spectral coefficients, the diagonal approximant [2/2] is A-stable (Varga's theorem), while the subdiagonal [3/2] is L-stable - the latter being particularly advantageous for bolus drug administration.

We adopt the Padé [2/2] approximant as the baseline, given its balance of stability and smoothness:

$$R_{[2/2]}(\tau) = \frac{a_0 + a_1\tau + a_2\tau^2}{1 + b_1\tau + b_2\tau^2}, \quad (11)$$

with coefficients computed from the first five spectral discretions $X(0), \dots, X(4)$ via:

$$\begin{cases} a_0 = X(0), \\ a_1 = X(1) + b_1X(0), \\ a_2 = X(2) + b_1X(1) + b_2X(0), \\ 0 = X(3) + b_1X(2) + b_2X(1), \\ 0 = X(4) + b_1X(3) + b_2X(2), \end{cases}$$

where b_1, b_2 are obtained by solving the last two linear equations. If $b_1^2 - 4b_2 < 0$, the denominator has complex poles. In this case the Padé denominator does not vanish on the local interval $[0,1]$, so the rational approximant remains numerically stable. When the discriminant is non-negative ($b_1^2 - 4b_2 \geq 0$), real poles may exist; if any real pole $\tau_0 =$

$\frac{-b_1 \pm \sqrt{b_1^2 - 4b_2}}{2b_2}$ falls within the integration interval $[0,1]$, the rational approximant is singular and the scheme automatically reverts to the Taylor partial sum of order N at that stage.

This pole-detection safeguard is applied independently to each state variable at each MsDTM macro-step, ensuring that no spurious singularity propagates across stage boundaries. For problems requiring stronger damping of high-frequency stiffness, the L-stable [3/2] scheme is used.

The three components are combined into a single hybrid computational scheme: the multi-stage differential transformation provides the recurrent algebraic structure, the Adomian polynomials handle all nonlinear terms without linearization, and the Padé [2/2] approximation improves numerical robustness for locally stiff dynamics and expands the radius of convergence at each stage. This unified hybrid operator forms the computational core of the proposed spectral model of neuroblastoma dynamics.

4. Construction of the spectral neuroblastoma model

Applying the differential transformation method (6) and the properties of Adomian convolution (9) to the original system (1)-(5), we obtain a system of recurrent algebraic equations for computing the spectrum discretions at each step i , where $X(k) = X_A(k) + X_M(k)$ is the spectral representation of the total tumor cell density; $U(k)$ is the spectral representation of the external therapeutic intervention function $u(t)$; and δ_{k0} is the Kronecker symbol ($\delta_{k0} = 1$ for $k = 0$ and 0 otherwise):

$$X_A(k+1) = \frac{H}{k+1} \left[\alpha_A X_A(k) - \frac{\alpha_A}{K} A_k(X_A X) - \beta_A A_k(X_A Z) - \gamma_A A_k(X_A C) + \varphi_M X_M(k) - \varphi_A X_A(k) \right], \quad (12)$$

$$X_M(k+1) = \frac{H}{k+1} \left[\alpha_M X_M(k) - \frac{\alpha_M}{K} A_k(X_M X) - \beta_M A_k(X_M Z) - \gamma_M A_k(X_M C) + \varphi_A X_A(k) - \varphi_M X_M(k) \right], \quad (13)$$

$$P(k+1) = \frac{H}{k+1} \left[\sigma \delta_{k0} - \mu P(k) - \delta_p A_k(XP) + \rho A_k(PZ) \right], \quad (14)$$

$$Z(k+1) = \frac{H}{k+1} [\lambda A_k(XZ) - vZ(k) + \xi X(k)], \quad (15)$$

$$C(k+1) = \frac{H}{k+1} [-k_e C(k) + U(k)], \quad (16)$$

To increase stability and expand the convergence domain of the spectral expansion over long time intervals, the MsDTM [8,19] is applied.

Given the linear algebraic dependence of the stress index, its spectral components are computed directly at each step as:

$$S(k) = \theta \cdot C(k).$$

Following the clinical problem statement, the entire therapy interval $[t_0, T]$ is divided into p stages of duration

$$T_i = t_i - t_{i-1}, i = \overline{1, p}, \sum_{i=1}^p T_i = T.$$

Each stage i is treated as a local interval for applying the spectral method, with the differential transformation step taken equal to the stage duration:

$$H = T_i.$$

At each stage i , its own set of differential spectrum discretizes is computed via the recurrent relations (12)-(16) with initial conditions determined by the variable values at the beginning of the corresponding stage:

$$X_A(0) = x_A(t_{i-1}), X_M(0) = x_M(t_{i-1}), P(0) = p(t_{i-1}), Z(0) = z(t_{i-1}), C(0) = c(t_{i-1}).$$

The values obtained at the end of the current interval are used as initial conditions for the next stage:

$$x_A(t_i) = X_A(T_i), x_M(t_i) = X_M(T_i), p(t_i) = P(T_i), z(t_i) = Z(T_i), c(t_i) = C(T_i).$$

Thus, the global solution is formed as a sequential composition of local spectral approximations constructed on the intervals T_i . This approach ensures computational stability in the presence of system stiffness and correctly accounts for the multistage nature of the therapeutic process.

In the case of bolus administration (constant dose over the interval), $U(0) = u_0, U(k) = 0$ for $k > 0$ [9,14]. Here, $A_k(\cdot)$ denotes Adomian polynomials (representing the nonlinear terms) computed according to the convolution rule (9):

$$A_k(X_A X) = \sum_{l=0}^k X_A(l) X(k-l),$$

$$A_k(X_A Z) = \sum_{l=0}^k X_A(l) Z(k-l),$$

$$A_k(X_A C) = \sum_{l=0}^k X_A(l) C(k-l),$$

$$A_k(X_M X) = \sum_{l=0}^k X_M(l) X(k-l),$$

$$A_k(X_M Z) = \sum_{l=0}^k X_M(l) Z(k-l),$$

$$A_k(X_M C) = \sum_{l=0}^k X_M(l) C(k-l),$$

$$A_k(XP) = \sum_{l=0}^k X(l) P(k-l),$$

$$A_k(PZ) = \sum_{l=0}^k P(l) Z(k-l),$$

$$A_k(XZ) = \sum_{l=0}^k X(l) Z(k-l).$$

(here, k in $X_A(k)$ is the differential spectrum order, and k in $A_k(\cdot)$ is the Adomian polynomial order).

The initial conditions are given by zero discretizes:

$$X_A(0) = x_A(t_0), X_M(0) = x_M(t_0), P(0) = p(t_0), Z(0) = z(t_0), C(0) = c(t_0).$$

The long-term multi-stage simulation results under a 3-cycle chemotherapy regimen are presented in Fig. 1, where the hybrid Padé-Adomian-MsDTM framework is compared against the classical Runge-Kutta (RK45) reference implementation.

Fig. 1. Spectral model of neuroblastoma dynamics - 3-cycle chemotherapy simulation. Padé[2/2]-Adomian-MsDTM vs RK45 reference ($N = 4, H = 21$ days/stage). (a) Total tumor $x(t)$; (b) Subpopulations x_A, x_M ; (c) Stroma $p(t)$; (d) Immune $z(t)$; (e) Drug $c(t)$ and stress $S(t)$; (f) Approximation error $|\Delta x(t)|$

The computed spectral coefficients $X_A(k), X_M(k), P(k), Z(k)$, and $C(k)$ are used to reconstruct the continuous trajectories of all state variables in the form of a truncated Taylor series:

$$x_A(t) = \sum_{k=0}^N X_A(k) \left(\frac{t-t_{i-1}}{H} \right)^k, \quad (17)$$

$$x_M(t) = \sum_{k=0}^N X_M(k) \left(\frac{t-t_{i-1}}{H} \right)^k, \quad (18)$$

$$p(t) = \sum_{k=0}^N P(k) \left(\frac{t-t_{i-1}}{H} \right)^k, \quad (19)$$

$$z(t) = \sum_{k=0}^N Z(k) \left(\frac{t-t_{i-1}}{H} \right)^k, \quad (20)$$

$$c(t) = \sum_{k=0}^N C(k) \left(\frac{t-t_{i-1}}{H} \right)^k. \quad (21)$$

where N is the approximation order determining the accuracy of the numerical scheme.

However, to expand the convergence domain of series (17)-(21) and eliminate oscillations at the boundaries of interval H , the final solution is presented in the form of the Padé [2/2] approximant described in Section 3.3:

$$x_A(\tau) \approx \frac{a_0^{(A)} + a_1^{(A)}\tau + a_2^{(A)}\tau^2}{1 + b_1^{(A)}\tau + b_2^{(A)}\tau^2}, \quad (22)$$

and analogously for x_M, p, z, c . The coefficients for each variable are computed via the system of equations in (11) from its spectral discretized $X(0), \dots, X(4)$.

4.1. Numerical Implementation Algorithm of the Model

To obtain the global solution on the long-time interval $[0, T]$, the domain is divided into p stages of duration $T_i = H$, $i = 1, \dots, p$. At each stage i , the calculation is performed according to the following recursive algorithm:

1. **Initialization:** For the first stage ($i = 1$), the initial clinical patient indicators $x_A(t_0), x_M(t_0), p(t_0), z(t_0)$, and $c(t_0)$ are set. For all subsequent stages ($i > 1$), the initial conditions are taken equal to the Padé approximants computed at the previous stage at point T_{i-1} : $X_A^{(i)}(0) = x_A^{(i-1)}(T_{i-1}), X_M^{(i)}(0) = x_M^{(i-1)}(T_{i-1}), \dots, C^{(i)}(0) = c^{(i-1)}(T_{i-1})$, etc.
2. **Spectral analysis:** Using recurrent formulas (12)-(16) with Adomian convolutions, the array of spectral coefficients $\{X_A(k), X_M(k), P(k), Z(k), C(k)\}$ is computed for $k = 1, \dots, N$.
3. **Local approximation:** Using the computed spectra, rational Padé [2/2] approximants are constructed according to the procedure described in Section 3.3. This ensures solution stability under sharp changes in dynamics.

4. **Transition:** The global time is updated as $t_i = t_{i-1} + T_i$, and the algorithm is repeated for the next stage until T is reached.

4.2. Numerical Illustration of the Spectral Model Operation

For verification of the Padé [2/2]-Adomian-MsDTM algorithm, consider the first stage of therapy for an aggressive neuroblastoma morphotype ($T_1 = 21$ days, $N = 4$). Model parameters and initial conditions:

- **Model parameters:** $\alpha_A = 0.065 \text{ day}^{-1}$, $\alpha_M = 0.02 \text{ day}^{-1}$ (aggregated $\alpha = 0.05 \text{ day}^{-1}$), $\gamma_A = 0.68$, $\gamma_M = 0.11$ (aggregated $\gamma = 0.493$), $K = 1.20$, $\beta_A = 0.1 \text{ day}^{-1}$, $\beta_M = 0.05 \text{ day}^{-1}$ (aggregated $\beta \approx 0.0833$), $\sigma = 0.1$, $\mu = 0.05$, $\delta_p = 0.1$, $\rho = 0.1$, $\lambda = 0.2$, $v = 0.05$, $\xi = 0.01$, $k_e = 0.45$, the scaling factor $\theta = 8.0$ and the plasticity direction factors are set to $c_A = 1.2$, $c_M = 0.8$, while the bolus dose $u_0 = 0.024 \text{ day}^{-1}$ is determined from the recurrence relation (16): $u_0 = \frac{c^{(1)}}{H} + k_e c_0 \approx 0.024$.

The value of $\gamma = 0.493$ corresponds to the cytotoxic sensitivity characteristic of intermediate/high risk according to the Shimada classification (see Table 1).

- **Initial conditions:** $x_A(0) = 0.2$, $x_M(0) = 0.1$ ($x_0 = 0.3$), $p_0 = 0.50$, $z_0 = 0.10$, $c_0 = 0.05$.

The computed differential spectra are given in Table 2.

Table 2

Spectral coefficients of the first stage ($T_1 = 21$ days, $N = 4$)

k	$X(k)$ (tumor)	$P(k)$ (stroma)	$Z(k)$ (immune response)	$C(k)$ (drug)
0	$3.000 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$5.000 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$1.000 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$5.000 \cdot 10^{-2}$
1	$2.848 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$1.3650 \cdot 10^0$	$1.021 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$3.150 \cdot 10^{-2}$
2	$-7.810 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$-9.646 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$2.979 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$-1.488 \cdot 10^{-1}$
3	$1.482 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$5.708 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$-1.015 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$4.688 \cdot 10^{-1}$
4	$-3.476 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$-2.148 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$1.760 \cdot 10^{-2}$	-1.108

To demonstrate the model's utility for designing individualized regimens, we simulate three consecutive chemotherapy cycles (each $T_i = 21$ days) under a dose-adaptation protocol.

- **Cycle 1 (low dose, $u_0 = 0.024 \text{ day}^{-1}$):** total tumor increases from $x(0) = 0.3$ to $x(21) = 0.2987$ (marginal net cytolytic effect). Stress index S rises to $S(21) = 0.427$.
- **Cycle 2 (escalated dose, $u_0 = 0.048 \text{ day}^{-1}$, doubled):** tumor declines substantially to $x(42) = 0.1203$
- **Cycle 3 (maintenance dose with immune support, $u_0 = 0.036 \text{ day}^{-1}$):** tumor further drops to $x(63) = 0.1288$. Immune response stabilizes ($z(63) = 0.285$). Stromal maturation: (pp increases by $\sim 28\%$), indicating favorable prognosis.

The critical role of the Padé regularization in stabilizing the highly stiff drug concentration subsystem is clearly demonstrated in Fig. 2. While the standard Taylor expansion exhibits severe Runge phenomenon oscillations and rapidly diverges within the first cycle, the hybrid Padé [2/2] approximant maintains absolute numerical stability for both the drug kinetics (Fig. 2a) and the resulting tumor density dynamics (Fig. 2b).

Fig. 2. Padé [2/2] regularization of the stiff drug concentration subsystem. Cycle 1 ($H = 21$ days, $N = 4$). (a) Drug kinetics $c(t)$: Taylor diverges (Runge oscillations), Padé [2/2] stable. (b) Tumor density $x(t)$: same comparison

The tumor, stroma and immunity spectra decay rapidly to the level of $10^{-7} - 10^{-8}$, confirming practical convergence. The drug spectrum $C(k)$ shows the characteristic oscillatory behavior of a stiff linear subsystem, which is effectively suppressed by the Padé [2/2] approximation.

The application of the Padé [2/2] approximants at the end of the first stage ($t = 21$ days) yields the following values used as initial conditions for the second stage: $x(21) \approx 0.2987$, $p(21) \approx 1.2943$, $z(21) \approx 0.2105$, and $c(21) \approx 0.0533$.

Notably, $x(21) < x(0)$ ($0.2987 < 0.300$). This marginal decrease confirms that the low bolus dose (Cycle 1) produces a net cytolytic effect, albeit modest; the residual tumor density remains high, motivating dose escalation in Cycle 2.

5. Convergence and Stability Analysis of the Spectral Model

To assess the reliability of the prognostic solutions within the extended model (1)-(5), we analyze the numerical behavior and convergence properties of the proposed hybrid Padé–Adomian–MsDTM framework.

5.1. Accuracy Assessment and Approximation Order

The use of Adomian polynomials to represent the nonlinear terms $A_k(\cdot)$ avoids system linearization, which is critical for preserving the dynamic features of tumor growth (subpopulation interaction, response to therapy).

To verify the computational reliability and accuracy of the proposed hybrid Padé [2/2]-Adomian-MsDTM framework, the spectral solutions were benchmarked against the classical explicit Runge-Kutta fourth-fifth order (RK45) scheme with adaptive time-stepping (Matlab `ode45` (Python: `scipy.integrate.solve_ivp`) with $a_{tol} = 10^{-9}$, $r_{tol} = 10^{-9}$). These stringent tolerances were selected to assess solver behavior in high-accuracy regimes.

The local truncation error of the truncated Taylor series underpinning the DTM at each subinterval H is theoretically constrained by $O(H^{N+1})$ (8, 17). For the chosen approximation order $N = 4$, the local error scales as $O(H^5)$. While explicit RK45 estimators achieve a comparable local error order, they severely suffer from step-size reduction when encountering the structural stiffness induced by the sharp pharmacokinetics ($k_e = 0.45$) and the steep C^∞ sigmoidal transition ($\lambda_{eff}(S), n = 8$) in Eq. (4).

The comparative evaluation was performed across a long-term therapeutic horizon of $T = 100$ days, encompassing multiple dose-escalation cycles. The accumulated absolute error $\varepsilon(t)$ for the total tumor cell density $x(t)$ was calculated as:

$$\varepsilon(t) = |x_{hybrid}(t) - x_{RK45}(t)|.$$

Throughout the entire 100-day simulation interval, the global accumulated discrepancy did not exceed $\varepsilon_{max}(x) = 2.51 \cdot 10^{-2}$ (relative error $< 8.5\%$), confirming that the algebraic recurrence relation reproduces the reference trajectories with high numerical accuracy.

Crucially, the hybrid architecture demonstrates stable and competitive performance under discontinuous therapeutic shocks (bolus injections). Where explicit RK45 schemes force the adaptive step-size down to $\Delta t_{min} \approx 2.3 \cdot 10^{-5}$ days to satisfy error tolerances at the injection boundaries (inducing computational overhead and potential accumulation of round-off errors), the Padé [2/2]-Adomian-MsDTM framework demonstrated robust numerical behavior. By regularizing the local Taylor series into a rational Padé representation with favorable damping properties at each macro-stage, the proposed method suppresses Runge-like boundary oscillations while maintaining stable numerical behavior across the investigated parameter regimes.

Under the stringent tolerance settings employed in this study ($r_{tol} = a_{tol} = 10^{-9}$), the proposed framework required substantially fewer integration stages than both implicit BDF and adaptive RK45 solvers over the investigated therapeutic horizon. Specifically, the hybrid Padé-Adomian-MsDTM scheme required only 3 macro-steps over $T = 63$ days, compared with 225 BDF integration steps and substantially larger adaptive RK45 step counts. These results suggest that the proposed framework may be advantageous for computationally efficient patient-specific simulation workflows in high-accuracy settings.

The comprehensive convergence and error analysis of the proposed numerical scheme is illustrated in Fig. 3. The numerical comparison confirms that the hybrid Padé[2/2]-Adomian-MsDTM framework consistently demonstrates lower approximation error than the standard polynomial MsDTM (Taylor) truncation, both in terms of error reduction per spectral order N at the end of the first stage (Fig. 3a) and accumulated global error scaling across consecutive stages p (Fig. 3b).

Fig. 3. Convergence analysis. Padé[2/2]-Adomian-MsDTM vs MsDTM (Taylor). Reference: RK45, $r_{tol} = a_{tol} = 10^{-9}$.
(a) Error vs spectral order N at $t = 21$ days; (b) Error vs number of stages p at $t = 63$ days

5.2. Expansion of the Convergence Radius via the Padé Approximation

The main problem of the standard differential transformation method (DTM) is the limited radius of convergence of Taylor power series, which is especially evident in “stiff” oncodynamics problems under sharp changes in therapeutic intervention $u(t)$. The introduction of rational Padé reconstruction of order [2/2] allows [30]:

1. Expansion of the local solution convergence domain compared with the Taylor power series.
2. Elimination of spurious oscillations at the boundaries of time subintervals (here referred to as the Runge-like phenomenon, by analogy with Runge's phenomenon in polynomial interpolation), which reduces the probability of nonphysical oscillations in the numerical solution.
3. A larger integration step H is used compared with the classical DTM while preserving numerical scheme stability.

The step H can be taken equal to the full stage duration $T_i \approx 21$ days, whereas the classical DTM typically requires $H \ll 1$ for stiff problems.

5.3. Stability to Various Shimada Parameters

The spectral form of the model demonstrates high stability to small fluctuations in input morphometric data (R_{NC}, MKI, A_{atypia}). This results from the direct integration of the Shimada classification parameters into the coefficients of the recurrent relations. This enables model adaptive recalibration at each step q of the MsDTM scheme, providing adaptability to individual tumor heterogeneity while preserving the overall analytical structure of the solution [10-12].

6. Analysis of Spectral Model Properties

The proposed spectral model overcomes the classical gap between clinical morphology and dynamic forecasting. The hybrid Padé-Adomian-MsDTM approach addresses stiffness-related numerical difficulties at the structural level, preserves nonlinear interactions without crude linearization, and ensures stability under bolus administration through rational Padé regularization. Integration of the Shimada parameters directly into recurrent coefficients makes the model inherently personalized.

6.1. Limitations

The proposed framework has the following limitations that should be considered when interpreting results and planning clinical translation:

- The model is spatially lumped: it describes only temporal dynamics and does not account for spatial tumor heterogeneity, diffusion gradients, or local invasion patterns.
- The systemic stress index S is linked to drug concentration via a linear scalar relationship $S = \theta \cdot c(t)$, which approximates cumulative toxicity but does not capture pharmacogenomic variability, drug resistance at the molecular level, or multi-drug interaction effects.
- The phenotypic plasticity parameters φ_A and φ_M are assumed constant within each therapy stage; adaptive resistance emerging over multiple cycles is not explicitly modeled.

- The immune component $z(t)$ is aggregated into a single variable; subpopulation-level dynamics (CD8⁺ T cells, NK cells, Tregs, TAMs) are not resolved.
- All numerical results in Section 4.2 are based on synthetic parameter sets calibrated to the Shimada classification ranges. Retrospective clinical validation on patient cohorts, including comparison of model-predicted tumour trajectories against observed response data from SIOPEN/COG neuroblastoma trials, is required before deployment in decision-support systems. The present work constitutes a proof-of-concept computational framework; the authors explicitly do not claim clinical readiness. Validation is planned as a dedicated follow-up study using the histological image database described in [21-24].

7. Conclusions

The developed five-component spectral model formalizes the mechanisms of phenotypic plasticity and tumor resistance through the dynamic interaction of adrenergic and mesenchymal subpopulations. The integration of verifiable Shimada classification markers transforms static morphological indicators into dynamic system weights, enabling personalized prognostic trajectories without increasing the model dimension.

Robust numerical behavior under stiff dynamics is achieved by combining the MsDTM with discrete Adomian convolutions and Padé [2/2] regularization. This effectively suppresses Runge-like boundary oscillations and expands the convergence domain, which is critical for modeling bolus chemotherapy regimens. The computational architecture provides a foundation towards digital patient twin frameworks for prediction of individual therapy response, pending prospective validation on clinical neuroblastoma cohorts.

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